

STUDY OF RAINFALL PATTERN AND COMPUTATIONS OF DEPTH OF RAINFALL FOR SUKHI DAM CATCHMENT AREA.

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ABSTRACT

The Gujarat state lies in the North-East corner of the coast of Western India. The rainfall pattern in the state varies drastically from north to south and east to west. The Sukhi Dam is constructed on River Sukhi; it is a tributary of River Orsang. Catchment area of Sukhi dam is 411.81 sq km, Orsang River, with a latitude of 21.97 (21° 58' 0 N) and a longitude of 73.47 (73° 28' 0 E), is a hydrographic (stream) located in India. A critical study is essential for studying the rainfall pattern and finding out the average depth of rainfall for the Sukhi dam catchment area.

In this paper, it is proposed to study the rainfall pattern and derive the average depth for the catchment of Sukhi Dam. For this study it is proposed to develop Thiessen polygons for Sukhi Dam catchment area and from that average depth of rainfall is calculated for different rain gauge stations located within the catchment area.

KEY WORDS

Rainfall, Catchment, Average Depth of Rainfall, Thiessen polygon method

OBJECTIVES OF STUDY

- (1) Analysis of rainfall pattern for various rain-gauge stations.
- (2) To find out average depth of rainfall of Sukhi Dam catchment area.

ABOUT THE STUDY AREA

Sukhi River is a tributary of River Orsang. Catchment area of Sukhi dam is 411.81 sq km. Besides the Sardar Sarovar Project (SSP), it is also proposed to construct a weir at Garudeshwar and a barrage at Bhadbhut on the downstream of the Sardar Sarovar Dam. Sukhi dam is located at the village: Sagodhara, Tal: pavi, Dis: Vadodara.

The catchment area of Sukhi Dam along with catchment areas of Sardar sarovar Dam and Proposed Bhadbhut barrage are given below in fig 1. The catchment area consist four Rain gauge stations namely Devgarh baria, Jambugoda, Chotta Udaipur, Jetpur For the analysis; data of rainfall are collected from State water data centre, Gandhinagar, and Narmada water resources and Kalpsar department, Gandhinagar.

Figure 1 Catchment area of Sukhi Dam.

RAINFALL PATTERN ANALYSIS

To find out average depth of rainfall for Sukhi Dam catchment area, Thiessen polygon method is adopted for analysis. For that Thiessen polygons are developed from the available rainfall data for each rain gauge station (as given below).

Fig 2 shows the Thiessen polygon for Sukhi Dam catchment area, fig 3 to 13 shows the rainfall at each year for different rain gauge stations.

Figure 2 Thiessen polygon for the Sukhi Dam Catchment area

Figure 4 Rainfall for year 1997

Figure 5 Rainfall for year 1998

Figure 3 Rainfall for year 1996

Figure 6 Rainfall for year 1999

Figure 7 Rainfall for year 2000

Figure 11 Rainfall for year 2004

Figure 8 Rainfall for year 2001

Figure 12 Rainfall for year 2005

Figure 9 Rainfall for year 2002

Figure 13 Rainfall for year 2006

Figure 10 Rainfall for year 2003

The average depth of rainfall for each year using the Thiessen Polygon method as well as the Arithmetic Mean Method is obtained as shown in Table 1

Table 1 Average Depth of Rainfall in mm over Sukhi Dam Catchment

Year	By Thiessen Polygon Method	By Arithmetic Mean Method
1996	1249	1214
1997	1197	1166
1998	1086	1112
1999	472	441
2000	283	278
2001	835	858
2002	825	833
2003	1054	1168
2004	1170	1209
2005	809	844
2006	1477	1479
Average	951	964

DISCUSSIONS & CONCLUSIONS

The average depth of rainfall calculated using both the methods for a span of 11 years for all the years from 1996 to 2006. For all of the years, the values obtained by both the methods are very near to the value obtained by the other method. Taking an average value for all the 11 years, we get Average depth of rainfall for Sukhi Dam Catchment as 951 mm using Thiessen Polygon Method and 964 mm using Arithmetic Mean Method.

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